

Short communication

Micro-encapsulation of Si-Fe ultra-high temperature phase change material: Fabrication and basic energy storage properties

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ABSTRACT

A micro-encapsulation technique has been proposed as an efficient way to protect metallic phase change materials (PCM) against degradation of its properties due to environmental and corrosion effects. So far, this technique has been mostly applied to Al-based metallic PCMs operating at temperatures below 700 °C and giving storing capacities of 180–370 Jg⁻¹. In this work, a micro-encapsulation approach was introduced for the first time to a binary eutectic Si-Fe ultra-high temperature PCM predicted to work at temperatures even higher than 1200 °C and providing few times larger stored energy (at a level of 1000 Jg⁻¹). A multi-step processing was designed and applied to fabricate spherical microcapsules having a structure of SiO₂ shell and the Si-Fe eutectic PCM core. Structure and basic thermophysical properties of Si-Fe microcapsules were experimentally validated in scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies. It was documented that the newly developed Si-Fe microcapsules exhibit high thermal energy storage density of ~1 MWh/m³, strongly exceeding capabilities of lead-acid and Li-ion batteries, as well as these of the current state of the art latent heat thermal energy storage systems utilized in concentrated solar power applications.

1. Introduction

Latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) has been established as a site-independent and highly effective way for supporting concentrated solar power (CSP) systems during blackout periods. It has been documented that CSP plants can provide a solar-to-electricity conversion efficiency rates of ~60 to even 80 % (as compared to average efficiency of 21–23 % for commercial solar panels in 2024) [1], if an operational temperature is high enough and properly set accordingly to a supported “engine”. For example, for steam generators temperature of a storing system should be in the range of 500–700 °C, while for Brayton cycles it is optimized for 700–900 °C [2–4]. Furthermore, metallurgical industrial processes and the most advanced ultrahigh temperature thermophotovoltaic (TPV) heat-to-electricity converters require temperatures as high as $T > 1200$ °C [5,6].

A phase change material (PCM) which is a substance able to store/

release energy under a solid to liquid transition, is located in a heart of each LHTES system. It is necessary to select a PCM that would exhibit a temperature of phase transition within specific operational conditions of an integrated power generator. Among various PCM candidates (paraffin wax, fatty acids or molten salts), metals and alloys are highly predisposed to be applied in high and ultra-high temperature (UHT) applications (i.e. even above 1000 °C). They combine a high thermal conductivity and high volumetric energy storage density (both few-times higher than the abovementioned counterparts). The main issues coming from using metallic PCMs are related to a generally high reactivity of molten metals towards contacting materials (including refractories used to build a container). Therefore, to protect a metallic PCM against degradation of its storing properties, a proper encapsulation ought to be considered.

A micro-encapsulation is a technique allowing fabrication of core/shell structures made of a PCM and oxide based outer layer. This method

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isolates a PCM from the harmful environmental effects and provides a high surface area for the heat transfer. Basic requirements for an effective encapsulation include:

- rounded shapes or spherical particles;
- very limited thermal volumetric expansion during melting/solidification;
- a formation of thick, continuous and thermally stable surface (oxide) shell.

In practice, it is implemented through a proper thermochemical treatment of spherical powders transforming them into microcapsules. Recently reported literature works on this topic (with a great contribution of Nomura et al.) are mostly limited to pure aluminum [7,8], eutectic Al-12Si [9,10] or hypereutectic Al-25Si alloys [11,12]. Various fabrication methods have been applied to produce Al-based microcapsules including sol-gel technique, controlled oxidation, hydrothermal treatment or steam oxidation. Al and Al-Si alloys provide a latent heat of fusion (ΔH_f) in the range of $\sim 180\text{--}370\text{ Jg}^{-1}$ at $T\sim 580\text{--}660\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Furthermore, it has been also documented that the Al-based microcapsules can survive up to 3000 consecutive melting/solidification cycles without a prominent degradation of their thermal properties (the ΔH_f value has remained at the level of 90 % of the non-cycled material) [13]. Nevertheless, to our best knowledge there is a complete lack of information regarding a feasibility of using this approach to UHT PCMs.

This work is focused on new materials technologies for CSP power generation by means of thermophotovoltaic energy converters combined with LHTES based on PCMs operating at temperature even above $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [14]. Therefore, we are targeting a completely new group of metallic PCMs that would strongly overcome Al-based alloys in terms of storing capacities. In this regard, a selection of Si as the main PCM's constituent is justified by its melting point of $T_m=1414\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, very high $\Delta H_f=1800\text{ Jg}^{-1}$ (which is the second highest value after boron) and thermal conductivity of $\lambda=140\text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. Beside of being highly reactive towards most of ceramic materials [15,16], pure Si cannot be used as a PCM because of its "water-like" behavior during solidification that is characterized by a volumetric expansion of $\sim 10\%$ [17]. It may lead to a destruction of a storing container. For the same reason, pure Si is not predisposed to be subjected to a micro-encapsulation processing. Therefore, a proper alloying is needed to increase applicability of Si-based PCMs.

The main goal of the present paper is to show the results of pioneering research on the micro-encapsulation of the Si-Fe eutectic alloy, as a new promising candidate to be applied as the UHT PCM.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material development and processing

The Si-Fe phase diagram and thermodynamic properties of Si-Fe alloys were investigated by using FactSage 8.1 software powered by FactPS and FTLite databases. The Equilib module of FactSage was applied to calculate ΔH_f values, by assuming a mass of the alloy of $m = 100\text{ g}$. After that, the selected SiFe43 (wt %) eutectic alloy was produced by an induction melting of a mixture of commercial low carbon FeSi75 ferrosilicon (Elkem, Norway) and pure Fe (99.99 %) (ThermoFisher, Norway). During this step, a mixture of raw materials was heated up to $T = 1500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and then cast to a graphite crucible under argon protective atmosphere. The chemical composition of the as-cast alloy was experimentally checked by the ICP-SFMS method (ALS Scandinavia AB Luleå, Sweden). Then, in order to transform the Si-Fe alloy ingots into spherical powders, the material was subjected to an ultrasonic powder atomization method by utilizing AMAZEMET rePOWDER® (Poland) device [18].

After that, spherical SiFe43 powders were processed in a two-step encapsulation method. The powders were subjected to an

Fig. 1. The results of FactSage calculations: Si-Fe binary phase diagram (a); an enthalpy vs. T plot for the SiFe43 eutectic alloy.

impregnation in nano-silica suspension (particle size 40 nm, Struers, Germany) to activate particles' surface. A magnetic stirring of 7.5 wt% of SiFe43 powder mixture in silica suspension at room temperature for 24 h, was applied for this purpose. This concept has been partially adopted from the work by Han et al. [19] on the Al-Si alloy. After filtering and drying, the powders were subjected to a high temperature oxidation treatment at $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/24\text{ h}$ in air targeted to develop a continuous oxide shell.

2.2. Characterization

Structural characterization of the investigated materials was carried out by using a scanning electron microscope (FEI Scios, USA) equipped with the X-Ray energy dispersive spectroscopy detector and electron backscatter diffraction system (SEM/EDS/EBSD) (EDAX, TSL OIM Analysis 5 software, Netherlands). X-ray diffraction analyses were performed by using Panalytical Empyrean PiXcel3D machine with ICDD PDF-4+2020 database. A differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter, Germany) was used to experimentally quantify ΔH_f values and melting/solidifying temperature ranges. For each powder type (as-atomized or encapsulated) a DSC scan was performed within a temperature range of $20\text{--}1450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, by using heating/cooling rates of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, and under flowing argon atmosphere. To protect the alloy under undesired interaction, before each DSC tests alumina crucible walls' were sprayed with an inert h-BN coating [15,16,20]. For each powder type (as-atomized or encapsulated), three samples were tested in DSC experiments. Representative curves are presented in the paper as the scattering of recorded ΔH_f values was not higher than 5 %.

Fig. 2. The results of SEM/EBSD analyses of the SiFe43 alloy in the as-cast state.

Fig. 3. SEM images of the as-atomized SiFe43 spherical powders.

3. Results and discussion

The results of thermodynamic calculations for the Si-Fe eutectic alloy are given in Fig. 1. It was predicted that eutectic SiFe43 alloy is formed through the *eutectic reaction between liquid phase and (FeSi₂+Si) mixture*. The reaction takes place at 1213 °C (Fig. 1a) by involving ΔH_f of 1010 Jg⁻¹ (Fig. 1b). A similar value of the ΔH_f around 1000 J/g was recently reported by Wenzel et al. [21] for the Fe-50Si (wt%) alloy

The results of SEM/EDS/EBSD analyses (Fig. 2) showing a presence of FeSi₂ matrix and Si needle-like crystals confirmed that the as-cast SiFe43 alloy was characterized by the phase composition as-predicted

by thermodynamic calculations.

The as-cast ingot was successfully transformed into spherical powders by the ultrasonic powder atomization approach (Fig. 3). The resulted powders were characterized by a mean particle size of 61.6 μm (Q₁₀=36.6 μm; Q₅₀=48.5 μm; Q₉₀=117.6 μm) and spherical shape without visible morphological flaws as satellites etc. Furthermore, by using proper SEM imaging techniques, (Si+FeSi₂) dual phase structure of individual particles, was revealed (Fig. 3b).

The results of microscopic inspections of cross-sectioned encapsulated powders proved the formation of SiFe43/SiO₂ core/shell-like structure (Fig. 4a). What is important, an oxide shell having a

Fig. 4. The results of characterization of SiFe43/SiO₂ microcapsules by SEM/EDS (a) and XRD (b) techniques.

thickness of around 2–3 μm showed a fully continuous character. The proposed phase identification was confirmed in the XRD studies documenting an existence of a mixture of FeSi₂ and pure Si crystals in the as-atomized powders; and a formation of amorphous cristoballite-like structure after a full chemical and heat treatment procedure (Fig. 4b).

The ΔH_f values of as-atomized and encapsulated SiFe43 powders were examined in DSC experiments (Fig. 5).

Firstly, it is found that the results of DSC experiments show a very good agreement with the outcomes of thermodynamic calculations in terms of quantified ΔH_f (see Fig. 1b). The DSC measured ΔH_f of as-atomized powders is 988 Jg⁻¹ (vs. 1010 Jg⁻¹ as predicted by the FactSage). The DSC recorded peak temperature is slightly higher than the one predicted in the Si-Fe phase diagram ($T_e=1230$ vs. 1213 °C). However, this difference could be justified by the effect of continuous heating (in here at 10 °C/min) that normally results in some overshooting of thermal events during DSC experiments [22]. A slightly decreased value of ΔH_f (down to 860 Jg⁻¹) measured for the encapsulated Si-Fe powders should be related to a partial transformation of the Si-Fe alloy into SiO₂ shell. Indeed, the difference of 14 % can be explained when comparing the results of DSC measurements to a thickness of SiO₂ shell observed in SEM analyses. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that ΔH_f received for both powders and converted to MWh/m³ unit, still show very high values above 1. As it has been explained by Datas et al. [23] the energy storage density of ~1 MWh/m³ is 10–20 times higher than that of lead-acid batteries, 2–6 times than that of Li-ion batteries and 5–10 times than that of the current state of the art LHTES systems utilized in CSP applications.

Finally, in order to make a preliminary assessment of a thermal resistance of our microcapsulated PCMs, both the as-atomized and fully processed SiFe43 powders were subjected to a heat treatment at 1280 °C/1h. A temperature of this experiment was intentionally set as 50 °C above of the melting point of the investigated PCM.

The most important finding from this test followed by the SEM inspections is that the morphology of the encapsulated SiFe43 powders seemed to be not significantly affected by the heating at 1280 °C/1 h (Fig. 6a). On the other hand, non-protected (as-atomized) powders apparently underwent (partial) melting and agglomeration (Fig. 6b). Thus, these results provide a very first indication that the developed SiO₂ shell shows a high thermal stability and it effectively protects the SiFe43 PCM granules against external effects. Nevertheless, more experiments on thermocycling behavior of SiFe43 microcapsules are needed to ultimately confirm their usefulness in giving a proper support to CSP and TPV systems.

Fig. 5. The results of DSC characterization of SiFe43 powders in the as-atomized (a) and encapsulated (b) condition. The ΔH_f value expressed in MWh/m³ unit was calculated by using experimentally measured room temperature density of 4.5821 g/cm³.

Fig. 6. SEM images of SiFe43 powders in the encapsulated (a) and as-atomized (b) condition after a heat treatment at 1280 °C/1 h in air.

4. Conclusions and future remarks

In this work, we report for the first time a possibility of using the microencapsulation approach to produce ultra-high temperature Si-Fe based PCM microcapsules. The following conclusions are drawn from the obtained results:

1. Spherical SiFe43 powders were successfully fabricated by the ultrasonic atomization method.
2. The proposed processing allows producing SiFe43/SiO₂ core/shell PCM microcapsules.
3. The SiFe43/SiO₂ PCM microcapsules show promising properties to be used in LHTES systems operating at $T > 1200$ °C. The microcapsules exhibit the phase transition above 1200 °C and gives the latent heat of fusion of around 860 Jg⁻¹. This value converted to MWh/m³ strongly exceeds capabilities of lead-acid and Li-ion batteries, as well as these of the current state of the art LHTES systems utilized in CSP applications.
4. Future works on thermocycling properties of the microcapsules are needed to give a final assessment of their usefulness in LHTES systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wojciech Polkowski: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Paolo Lai Zhong Lo Biundo:** Resources, Investigation. **Jianmeng Jiao:** Investigation. **Maria Wallin:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Bartosz Kalicki:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Jakub Ciftci:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Łukasz Zrodowski:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Adelajda Polkowska:** Methodology, Investigation. **Aleksandra Bętkowska:** Methodology, Investigation. **Filip Kateusz:** Methodology, Investigation. **Merete Tangstad:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The raw data required to reproduce these findings are available from the Corresponding Author on demand.

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